

REVAMP THE EDUCATIONAL SSCENARIO TO FIX RTE ISSUES UNDER NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020

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ABSTRACT

National Education Policy 2020 is designed to strip education of its essence and wipe out whatever little of democratic education still exists in the country. After a meaningful silence for over a year, the present BJP-led Union government has made public a National Education Policy 2020 (NEP2020), an abridged reshuffled version of the Draft NEP 2019 (DNEP 2019) released in June last year. In both content of the Policy documents and the intent of the policymakers as well as in verbosity and flamboyance, the two match each other, though with some differences. So much so that, a section of intelligentsia and general people are mesmerized at the verbose presentation and flamboyant pledges to miss between-the-lines implications. In fact, verbosity and flamboyance of the content rather served for the government as a cover to conceal the intent, which in ultimate analysis comes down to blunt and vicious agglomeration of the entire attacks on education that had been continuing since independence, including in them the agenda of curtailment of education for the masses and doing away with all the nobilities and essence of a genuine education. Yet, there is a long road ahead of the NEP. Given its scale and the kind of complexity involved in its execution, particularly securing coordination and cooperation amongst diverse stakeholders at state, district, private sector amongst others, makes it a daunting exercise. Apart from this, one has to deal with weak state capacity, availability of financial resources and, most importantly, the education ecosystem that acts as a drag on new ideas and innovation. Yet, the most critical challenge before NEP is building consensus and getting states to own the first omnibus programme after 1986. In short, the success of the NEP largely hinges on cooperative federalism and states taking ownership of the reforms.

Introduction:

National Education Policy 2020 is designed to strip education of its essence and wipe out whatever little of democratic education still exists in the country. After a meaningful silence for over a year, the present BJP-led Union government has made public a National Education Policy 2020 (NEP2020), an abridged reshuffled version of the Draft NEP 2019 (DNEP 2019) released in June last year. In both content of the Policy documents and the intent of the policymakers as well as in verbosity and flamboyance, the two match each other, though with some differences. So much so that, a section of intelligentsia and general people are mesmerized at the verbose presentation and flamboyant pledges to miss between-the-lines implications. In fact, verbosity and flamboyance of the content rather served for the government as a cover to conceal the intent, which in ultimate analysis comes down to blunt and vicious agglomeration of the entire attacks on education that had been continuing since independence, including in them the agenda of curtailment of education for the masses and doing away with all the nobilities and essence of a genuine

education. However, the attempt proved abortive, as the NEP 2020 instantly gave rise to strong resentment from an overwhelmingly large section of academic and education fraternity from all corners of the country. Surprisingly for any democratic-minded person, the Union government made the announcement amidst the lockdown clamped on this huge country by none other than itself, that too under a meager 4-hour notice. During this lockdown people particularly the toiling masses were forced to remain engaged in fighting for their life and livelihood due to the tragic Covid 19 pandemic. Schools-colleges-offices were closed for indefinite time. There was no scope for discussions-exchanges-interactions in public. The situation continues still today. And apparently the government has taken it as rather another cover, to push through its agenda. Not only was that, such an important policy, a vital issue for the country and its people announced without any discussion in the Parliament. Nor there was involvement of representatives of any of the state governments in the process, though education is constitutionally in the Concurrent List and though in the measure of budget allocation on education in terms of GDP the Union government's share is only 10% of the state government's share. No educationist of national stature and name had any inkling of the oncoming announcement. To sum up. there was no meaningful debates- discussions-polemics in a way that were expected and essential to frame a national policy on an issue like education. Incidentally, the date of announcement, 29 July 2020, coincided with the 129th death anniversary of Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar, that too falling in the birth- bicentennial year of this great man of our immediate past, who had fought life-long for the cause of establishing genuine education system, including equipped teachers, proper institutions in the country.

ISSUES IN NEP 2020:

The new policy has tried to please all, and the layers are clearly visible in the document. It says all the right things and tries to cover all bases, often slipping off keel.

1. **Lack of integration:** In both the thinking, and in the document, there are lags, such as the integration of technology and pedagogy. There are big gaps such as lifelong learning, which should have been a key element of upgrading to emerging sciences.
2. **Language barrier:** There is much in the document ripe for debate – such as language. The NEP seeks to enable home language learning up to class five, in order to improve learning outcomes. Sure, early comprehension of concepts is better in the home language and is critical for future progress. If the foundations are not sound, learning suffers, even with the best of teaching and infrastructure. But it is also true that a core goal of education is social and economic mobility, and the language of mobility in India is English.
3. **Multilingualism debate:** Home language succeeds in places where the ecosystem extends all the way through higher education and into employment. Without such an ecosystem in place, this may not be good enough. The NEP speaks of multilingualism and that must be emphasised. Most classes in India are de facto bilingual. Some states are blissfully considering this policy as a futile attempt to impose Hindi.
4. **Lack of funds:** According to Economic Survey 2019-2020, the public spending (by the Centre and the State) on education was 3.1% of the GDP. A shift in the cost structure of education is inevitable. While funding at 6% of GDP remains doubtful, it is possible that parts of the transformation are achievable at a lower cost for greater scale.
5. **A move in haste:** The country is grappled with months of COVID-induced lockdowns. The policy had to have parliamentary discussions; it should have undergone a decent parliamentary debate and deliberations considering diverse opinions.
6. **Overambitious:** All aforesaid policy moves require enormous resources. An ambitious target of public spending at 6% of GDP has been set. This is certainly a tall order, given the current tax-to-GDP ratio and competing claims on the national exchequer of healthcare, national security and other key sectors. The exchequer itself is choked meeting the current expenditure.
7. **Pedagogical limitations:** The document talks about flexibility, choice, experimentation. In higher education, the document recognizes that there is a diversity of pedagogical needs. If it is a mandated option within single institutions, this will be a disaster, since structuring a curriculum for a

classroom that has both one-year diploma students and four-year degree students' takes away from the identity of the institution.

8. **Institutional limitations:** A healthy education system will comprise of a diversity of institutions, not a forced multi-disciplinarily one. Students should have a choice for different kinds of institutions. The policy risks creating a new kind of institutional isomorphism mandated from the Centre.
9. **Issues with examinations:** Exams are neurotic experiences because of competition; the consequences of a slight slip in performance are huge in terms of opportunities. So the answer to the exam conundrum lies in the structure of opportunity. India is far from that condition. This will require a less unequal society both in terms of access to quality institutions, and income differentials consequent upon access to those institutions.
10. There is a persistent mismatch between the knowledge & skills imparted and the jobs available. This has been one of the main challenges that have affected the Indian education system since Independence.
11. NEP 2020 failed to check this, as it is silent on education related to emerging technological fields like artificial intelligence, cyberspace, nanotech, etc.
12. An ambitious target of public spending at 6% of GDP has been set. Mobilising financial resources will be a big challenge, given the low tax-to-GDP ratio and competing claims on the national exchequer of healthcare, national security and other key sectors.
13. The policy has also been criticized due to the legal complexities surrounding the applicability of two operative policies namely The Right to Education Act, 2009 and the New Education Policy, 2020. Certain provisions such as the age of starting schooling will need to be deliberated upon, in order to resolve any conundrum between the statute and the recently introduced policy in the longer run.
14. It is pertinent to note that past attempts at parliamentary legislations under the erstwhile regulatory set up have not been successful. The failure can be attributed to the role of regulators and the intended legislative changes being out of alignment, as in the case of Foreign Educational Institutions (Regulation of Entry and Operations) Bill, 2010, which lapsed; and the proposed Higher Education Commission of India (Repeal of University Grants Commission Act) Act, 2018 which remained did not reach the Parliament.
15. While the Universities Grants Commission and the All India Council for Technical Education have played a major role, questions pertaining to the role of the UGC and AICTE remain unanswered under the new policy.
16. Doubling the Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education by 2035 which is one of the stated goals of the policy will mean that we must open one new university every week, for the next 15 years.

Five Suggestions for the New Education Policy:

Fix RTE related issues, universalize secondary education and replicate successful government school systems. The Human Resource Development (HRD) ministry has plans for a massive revamp of the educational scenario through its New Education Policy (NEP). A nationwide consultation process is underway, seeking inputs from all government educational agencies up to the gram panchayat level. The following suggestions are offered for better implementation of New Education Policy in true spirit.

1. Reformulate the RTE based on outcomes:

There is a dire need to revisit The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act (RTE)-2009. RTE has been successful in providing universal access to elementary education, increasing retention and improving school infrastructure. But it has failed to improve learning levels of children. The annual nationwide ASER (Annual Status of Education Report) shows that between 2009 and 2014, the reading

levels across India (barring a few Southern states) have either declined or stagnated. Basic arithmetic abilities of children have largely worsened all across the country. The government acknowledges this and has prioritized ensuring the learning outcomes in elementary education as the top priority in the consultation theme. It needs some introspection as to why, despite increased budgetary outlays, infrastructure and pupil teacher-norms through RTE, the learning levels are showing no signs of improvement. Perhaps the RTE Act is to be blamed. The Section 16 of RTE states that no child shall be expelled or held back in a class until he/she completes elementary schooling. Although this was done to remove the burden of exams and prevent dropouts, many teachers feel that this clause has dis-incentivized learning. They complain that rural kids don't even bother to attend exams citing reasons such as festivals or household events. RTE should do away with the gift of automatic promotion of students, and instead, may provide additional coaching and options of re-appearing in the exams in the same year for badly performing students. Along with this, there is a need for examination reforms.

The NEP consultation theme does stress the need for reforming the examination systems. It is evaluating the feasibility of adopting Continuous Comprehensive Examination (CCE), currently followed by the CBSE board, across all schools.

2. Improve public schools for quality and social integration:

Another mandate of RTE which needs careful rethinking is the one-size-fits all approach of reserving 25% of seats under Section 12 (1) (c) of the RTE Act in private schools for the weaker sections of the society. This clause was conceived to expand the options for poor parents to send their kids to private schools, an alibi for the voucher system. It reflects an implicit assumption by the government that private schools are better than the public schools. There is mixed evidence of whether private schools (barring a few elite schools in urban areas) fare better than public schools. The trend captured by ASER over ten years reveals that, although enrollment in private schools is increasing tremendously even among the poor in rural areas, learning levels have not showed any significant improvement. By mandating reservations in public schools, the Government is abdicating itself of its responsibility towards improving the quality of public schools.

Contrary to its original intent of integrating students of different economic backgrounds, reservation of seats in private schools has created segregation in schools. Many private schools show differential treatment towards these reserved students, and puts them in different sections, citing lack of preparedness as a reason for not being to compete with their regular students. Way back in 1966, the Kothari Commission had recommended Common School System (CSS) where kids from all socio-economic backgrounds study together and learn from each other's life experiences. It is essential to bring back the trust in public education system by improving its quality rather than turning blindly to private schools. The Government can learn from its success in schooling systems such as Kendriya Vidyalayas and Navodaya Vidyalayas, which have a proven track record of getting excellent results.

3. Increase budgetary allocation on education:

To improve the schooling system, budgetary allocations have to be increased. Right from the time of Kothari Commission, there has been repeated calls by educationalists, NGOs and policy analysts that the governments should allocate 6% of GDP towards education. However, Indian allocation for education has stuck between 3.5-4% of GDP. In recent times, there is an alarming trend of decreasing central funding to elementary education. An analysis by Accountability Initiative, Center for Policy Research and ASER reveals that central funding for SSA and mid day meal program has decreased from Rs 38,797 crore in 2013-14 to Rs 31, 236 crore in 2015-16.

4. Universalize Secondary Education:

India is close to achieving universal access to elementary education. However, elementary education is too basic to provide any life skills or vocational skills for productive employment. The next logical step for government should be to universalize secondary education. The Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA) was started in 2009 with the main objective to make secondary education of good quality available, accessible and affordable to all by 2020. One major initiative of RMSA was to set up 6000 Model Schools (one in every block) through state and public-private partnerships, as a benchmark of excellence for providing quality education. Unfortunately, because of the steep budget cuts, this fiscal year, secondary education has received diminished attention. In a major setback this year, the centre has totally delinked itself from the Model schools program, thereby widening the gap between promise and reality.

5. Replicate successful Government school systems:

To provide quality secondary education, the Government can look back at the successful system of Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalayas. Rajiv Gandhi had mooted the idea of setting up NVs in 1986, as part of the National Policy on Education (NPE) to nurture bright rural children. Navodaya Vidyalayas are fully residential rural schools with classes from VI- XIIth. There are about 590 NVs with two lakh students enrolled across all districts in India, barring Tamil Nadu. The performance of NV students in Xth and XIIth beats the all India average of other CBSE X schools, including Kendriya Vidyalayas. NV students regularly excel in many competitive exams like IITs, UPSC and IIMs among others, and also in sports and many co-curricular activities. The success of JNVs can be attributed to multiple factors like well-trained teachers who come from all across India, excellent academic and co-curricular infrastructure, and the residential nature of school. Studying under one roof integrates students from all socioeconomic backgrounds and corrects for the household factors that could have prevented students from active participation in academic and co-curricular activities.

The success of the JNVs has to be replicated on a larger scale even if it means substantial investment on every child. According to a recent report, the Government spent Rs 1905 crores on this in 2014-15, which translates to about Rs 85,000 per child. Expansion to all 6000 Talukas in India may cost around Rs. 20,000 crore, a small sum to raise the human capital of 20 lakh potential students when compared to typical physical infrastructure investments by government. Although India boasts of several research institutions of excellence, research in education is minimal. Most universities do not have any school of education, and none of the IITs and other IIXs have any department of education. NEP gives a golden opportunity to create comprehensive reforms in education and shape our future generation. It must not be wasted.

Conclusion:

To sum up, the NEP 2020 is truly a path breaking document in every sense. The policy, amongst others, aims to address pedagogical issues, structural inequities, broadening of access apart from making the learners future ready while meeting the demands of a 21st century India. Simultaneously, the NEP has the most challenging task of addressing multiple crises in the education system. Its effective implementation is critical if India wants to reap the demographic dividends and capitalize the opportunities from a rapidly growing knowledge economy. Given its transformative potentials, the Centre has shown urgency and a sense of purpose by launching a series of initiatives in the recent months notwithstanding the challenges of the pandemic. A number of states have officially launched the policy and many others are in the process to do the same. Yet, there is a long road ahead of the NEP. Given its scale and the kind of complexity involved in its execution, particularly securing coordination and cooperation amongst diverse stakeholders at state, district, private sector amongst others, makes it a daunting exercise. Apart from this, one has to deal with weak state capacity, availability of financial resources and, most importantly, the education ecosystem that acts as a drag on new ideas and innovation. Yet, the most critical challenge before NEP is building consensus and getting states to own the first omnibus programme after 1986. In short, the success of the NEP largely hinges on cooperative federalism and states taking ownership of the reforms.

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